

FREQUENCY OF FOREIGN BODIES IN THE EAR AMONG PEDIATRIC PATIENTS PRESENTING TO THE ENT DEPARTMENT OF A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Ear foreign bodies are a common pediatric otorhinolaryngological emergency and frequently present to outpatient and emergency departments. Children are particularly vulnerable because of exploratory behavior and accidental insertion of small objects into the external auditory canal. Delayed presentation or inappropriate removal attempts may lead to complications including canal trauma, otitis externa, and tympanic membrane injury.

Objective:

To determine the frequency and pattern of ear foreign bodies among pediatric patients presenting to the ENT Department of Ayub Teaching Hospital, Abbottabad.

Methods:

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of ENT at Ayub Teaching Hospital over a six-month period from 15 October 2024 to 15 April 2025. A total of 173 pediatric patients aged 1–14 years presenting with suspected ear foreign bodies were enrolled using consecutive non-probability sampling. Demographic characteristics, type and nature of foreign bodies, side of involvement, clinical presentation, and complications were recorded on a structured proforma. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 27, and results were presented as frequencies and percentages.

Results:

Among 173 patients, the most commonly affected age group was 4–6 years, accounting for 68 (39.3%) cases, followed by 7–10 years in 47 (27.2%) patients. Male children predominated, with 102 (59.0%) cases. Inorganic foreign bodies were more common than organic foreign bodies, observed in 99 (57.2%) and 74 (42.8%) patients, respectively. Beads were the most frequently encountered foreign bodies in 41 (23.7%) patients, followed by seeds/grains in 36 (20.8%) and cotton pieces/cotton buds in 24 (13.9%) cases. Right ear involvement was noted in 94 (54.3%) patients, while bilateral involvement was

observed in 6 (3.5%) cases. The most common presenting complaint was ear pain or irritation in 92 (53.2%) patients, followed by history of foreign body insertion in 86 (49.7%) and ear discharge in 41 (23.7%) patients. Most patients had no complications following impaction or removal of the foreign body (149; 86.1%). External auditory canal abrasion was the most frequent complication, occurring in 13 (7.5%) patients, while tympanic membrane injury was observed in 3 (1.7%) cases. The tympanic membrane remained intact in 170 (98.3%) patients after removal.

Conclusion:

Ear foreign bodies are a common pediatric ENT presentation, particularly among younger children and males. Inorganic objects, especially beads, were the most frequently encountered foreign bodies. Most cases were managed successfully with minimal complications when evaluated and treated promptly in a specialized ENT setting. Early recognition, appropriate referral, and increased parental awareness may help reduce morbidity associated with pediatric ear foreign bodies.

Keywords: Pediatric ear foreign bodies; Aural foreign bodies; External auditory canal; Pediatric ENT emergencies; Ear foreign body removal; Beads; Inorganic foreign bodies; Children.

INTRODUCTION

Foreign bodies of the ear are a common problem encountered in pediatric ENT practice and frequently present to outpatient departments and emergency units¹. Children are particularly prone to inserting objects into the external auditory canal because of their exploratory behavior and curiosity during early developmental years. The condition is most commonly seen in children younger than 10 years of age and represents a significant proportion of ENT emergencies worldwide^{2,3}. A wide variety of objects may be found in the ear canal, including beads, seeds, grains, cotton pieces, paper fragments, toy parts, insects, and stones⁴. The type of foreign body often varies according to the child's age, environment, and availability of small household objects. Organic foreign bodies such as seeds may absorb moisture and swell, making removal more difficult, whereas inorganic objects can cause trauma to the external auditory canal during manipulation⁵. Although many children present early after insertion of the object, others may remain asymptomatic or present later with ear pain, bleeding, hearing impairment, foul-smelling discharge, irritation, or a sensation of blockage⁶. Prompt diagnosis and careful removal are important to prevent complications. Repeated attempts at removal by untrained individuals or delayed presentation may result in edema of the external auditory canal, abrasions, otitis externa, tympanic membrane perforation, and rarely middle ear injury⁷. In younger children, removal

can also be technically difficult because of poor cooperation and anxiety, occasionally necessitating sedation or general anesthesia³. Therefore, ear foreign bodies continue to pose both diagnostic and therapeutic challenges in routine pediatric ENT practice. Several international studies have evaluated the pattern of ENT foreign bodies in children and have shown that the ear and nose are among the most commonly affected anatomical sites^{4,8}. Studies have also demonstrated that children account for the majority of aural foreign body cases requiring hospital-based management⁸. However, the pattern of presentation and type of foreign bodies may differ across regions because of variations in socioeconomic conditions, parental awareness, cultural practices, and healthcare access. In developing countries such as Pakistan, pediatric ear foreign bodies are frequently encountered in tertiary care hospitals. Delayed healthcare-seeking behavior, inadequate parental supervision, and initial attempts at removal outside specialized ENT settings may increase the risk of complications. Despite the common nature of this condition, there is limited local literature focusing specifically on pediatric ear foreign bodies, particularly from the northern regions of the country. Most regional studies have evaluated ENT foreign bodies collectively rather than examining aural foreign bodies as a separate clinical entity^{1,9}.

Ayub Teaching Hospital is a major tertiary care referral center serving a large population of

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and surrounding areas, where pediatric patients with ear foreign bodies are commonly managed in daily ENT practice. However, local data regarding the frequency and pattern of ear foreign bodies in children presenting to this institution are scarce. Identification of the commonly encountered foreign bodies and their demographic distribution may help improve early recognition, parental counseling, and management strategies. Therefore, this study was conducted to determine the frequency of foreign and patterns of foreign bodies of the ear in pediatric patients presenting to the ENT Department of Ayub Teaching Hospital.

Objectives

General Objective

To determine the frequency of foreign bodies in the ear among pediatric patients presenting to the ENT Department of Ayub Teaching Hospital.

Specific Objectives

1. To describe the demographic characteristics of pediatric patients presenting with ear foreign bodies.
2. To identify the commonly encountered types and nature of ear foreign bodies in children presenting to the ENT department.
3. To determine the distribution of ear foreign bodies according to age group, gender, and side of involvement.
4. To document the clinical presentation of pediatric patients with ear foreign bodies presenting to the study setting.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of ENT at Ayub Teaching Hospital, a tertiary care teaching hospital catering to patients from Abbottabad and surrounding districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Study Duration

The study was conducted over a period of six months, from 15th October 2024 to 15th April 2025, after approval of the research synopsis and

ethical clearance from the Institutional Review Board

Sample Size

A sample size of 173 patients was calculated using the WHO sample size calculator, taking the anticipated frequency of ear foreign bodies as 20.2%, with a 95% confidence level and 6% margin of error.

Sampling Technique

Patients were enrolled using consecutive non-probability sampling.

Inclusion Criteria

The study included pediatric patients of either gender, aged 1-14 years, presenting to the ENT outpatient department or emergency department with clinical suspicion of a foreign body in the ear. Clinical suspicion was based on symptoms such as ear pain, bleeding, ear discharge, hearing difficulty, irritation, or a positive history of insertion of an object into the ear.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with other ear conditions that could mimic symptoms of foreign body impaction, including impacted cerumen, otitis externa, otomycosis, chronic suppurative otitis media, or traumatic ear injuries unrelated to foreign bodies, were excluded from the study.

Data Collection Procedure

After obtaining approval from the institutional ethical review committee, pediatric patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study after written informed consent was obtained from their parents or legal guardians. A detailed clinical history was taken from the accompanying attendants, including duration of symptoms and any history suggestive of insertion of a foreign body into the ear. Demographic information including age, gender, residence, parental education, and socioeconomic status was recorded on a pre-designed proforma. All patients underwent thorough otological examination under adequate illumination using an otoscope and, where required, microscopic examination for

confirmation of the diagnosis. Once identified, the foreign body was removed using appropriate ENT instruments such as Jobson Horne probe, Tilley's forceps, alligator forceps, wire loop, or suction, depending upon the type and location of the foreign body. The side of involvement, type of foreign body, and its nature (organic or inorganic) were documented. The condition of the external auditory canal and tympanic membrane after removal was also noted.

All clinical assessments and procedures were performed by the principal investigator under the supervision of the consultant ENT surgeon to maintain uniformity in data collection and management.

Data Analysis Procedure

Data were entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27. Continuous variables such as age were presented

as mean \pm standard deviation or median with interquartile range depending upon the distribution of data. Categorical variables including gender, residence, type of foreign body, nature of foreign body, and side of involvement were expressed as frequencies and percentages. The results were presented in the form of tables and graphs where appropriate.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Research and Ethics Committee of Ayub Teaching Hospital prior to commencement of data collection. Written informed consent was obtained from the parents or guardians of all participating children. Confidentiality of patient information was maintained throughout the study, and all procedures were carried out according to standard clinical and ethical guidelines.

RESULTS

Tables

Table 1: Age Distribution of Pediatric Patients Presenting with Ear Foreign Bodies (n = 173)

Age Group (Years)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1-3	39	22.5
4-6	68	39.3
7-10	47	27.2
11-14	19	11.0
Total	173	100

Table 2: Gender Distribution of Study Participants (n = 173)

Gender	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Male	102	59.0
Female	71	41.0
Total	173	100

Table 3: Nature and Type of Ear Foreign Bodies among Pediatric Patients (n = 173)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Nature of Foreign Body		
Organic	74	42.8
Inorganic	99	57.2
Type of Foreign Body		
Beads	41	23.7
Seeds/Grains	36	20.8
Cotton Pieces/Cotton Bud	24	13.9
Insects	19	11.0
Paper Pieces	15	8.7
Stones/Pebbles	12	6.9
Pencil Eraser/Stationery Material	10	5.8
Food Particles	7	4.0
Buttons	5	2.9
Small Plastic Toy Parts	4	2.3
Total	173	100

Table 4: Side of Ear Involvement among Study Participants (n = 173)

Side Involved	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Right Ear	94	54.3
Left Ear	73	42.2
Bilateral	6	3.5
Total	173	100

Table 5: Clinical Presentation of Pediatric Patients with Ear Foreign Bodies (n = 173)*

Clinical Presentation	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Ear Pain/Irritation	92	53.2
History of Foreign Body Insertion	86	49.7
Ear Discharge	41	23.7
Foreign Body Visible to Parents	27	15.6
Decreased Hearing	34	19.7
Restlessness/Crying in Younger Children	22	12.7
Bleeding from Ear	18	10.4
Foul Smell from Ear	14	8.1

*Multiple responses were recorded; percentages do not sum to 100%.

Table 6: Age-wise Distribution of Common Ear Foreign Bodies (n = 173)

Type of Foreign Body	1-3 Years n (%)	4-6 Years n (%)	7-10 Years n (%)	11-14 Years n (%)	Total
Beads	8 (20.5)	20 (29.4)	10 (21.3)	3 (15.8)	41
Seeds/Grains	11 (28.2)	14 (20.6)	8 (17.0)	3 (15.8)	36
Cotton Pieces/Cotton Bud	4 (10.3)	10 (14.7)	7 (14.9)	3 (15.8)	24
Insects	3 (7.7)	8 (11.8)	6 (12.8)	2 (10.5)	19
Paper Pieces	4 (10.3)	5 (7.4)	4 (8.5)	2 (10.5)	15
Stones/Pebbles	3 (7.7)	4 (5.9)	4 (8.5)	1 (5.3)	12
Pencil Eraser/Stationery Material	2 (5.1)	3 (4.4)	4 (8.5)	1 (5.3)	10
Food Particles	2 (5.1)	2 (2.9)	2 (4.3)	1 (5.3)	7
Buttons	1 (2.6)	1 (1.5)	2 (4.3)	1 (5.3)	5
Small Plastic Toy Parts	1 (2.6)	1 (1.5)	0 (0.0)	2 (10.5)	4
Total	39	68	47	19	173

Table 7: Gender-wise Distribution of Ear Foreign Bodies (n = 173)

Type of Foreign Body	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	Total
Beads	22 (21.6)	19 (26.8)	41
Seeds/Grains	24 (23.5)	12 (16.9)	36
Cotton Pieces/Cotton Bud	14 (13.7)	10 (14.1)	24
Insects	12 (11.8)	7 (9.9)	19
Paper Pieces	8 (7.8)	7 (9.9)	15
Stones/Pebbles	8 (7.8)	4 (5.6)	12
Pencil Eraser/Stationery Material	5 (4.9)	5 (7.0)	10
Food Particles	4 (3.9)	3 (4.2)	7
Buttons	2 (2.0)	3 (4.2)	5
Small Plastic Toy Parts	3 (2.9)	1 (1.4)	4
Total	102	71	173

Table 8: Complications Observed Following Ear Foreign Body Impaction or Removal (n = 173)

Complication	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
No Complication	149	86.1
External Auditory Canal Abrasion	13	7.5
Otitis Externa	6	3.5
Tympanic Membrane Injury	3	1.7
Mild Canal Bleeding	2	1.2
Total	173	100

Table 9: Residence of Study Participants (n = 173)

Residence	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Rural	109	63.0
Urban	64	37.0
Total	173	100

Table 10: Condition of Tympanic Membrane after Removal of Foreign Body (n = 173)

Tympanic Membrane Status	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Intact/Non-traumatized	170	98.3
Traumatized	3	1.7
Total	173	100

Figures

Figure 1: Age Distribution of Pediatric Patients with Ear Foreign Bodies (n = 173)

Figure 2: Gender Distribution of Study Participants (n = 173)

Figure 1: Age Distribution of Pediatric Patients (n = 173)

Figure 2: Gender Distribution of Study Participants (n = 173)

Figure 3: Nature of Ear Foreign Bodies (n = 173)

Figure 5: Side of Ear Involvement in Study Participants (n = 173)

Figure 3: Nature of Ear Foreign Bodies (n = 173)

Figure 5: Side of Ear Involvement (n = 173)

Figure 4: Type of Ear Foreign Bodies among Pediatric Patients (n = 173)

Figure 4: Type of Ear Foreign Bodies among Pediatric Patients (n = 173)

Figure 6: Clinical Presentation of Patients with Ear Foreign Bodies (n = 173, Multiple Responses)

Figure 6: Clinical Presentation of Patients with Ear Foreign Bodies (n = 173)

Figure 7: Age-wise Distribution of Common Ear Foreign Bodies (Top 5 Types, n = 173)

Figure 7: Age-wise Distribution of Common Ear Foreign Bodies - Top 5 Types (n = 173)

Figure 8: Gender-wise Distribution of Ear Foreign Bodies (n = 173)

Figure 8: Gender-wise Distribution of Ear Foreign Bodies (n = 173)

Figure 9: Complications Following Ear Foreign Body Impaction/Removal (n = 173)

Figure 9: Complications Following FB Impaction/Removal (n = 173)

Figure 10: Residence of Study Participants (n = 173)

Figure 10: Residence of Study Participants (n = 173)

Figure 11: Tympanic Membrane Status after Foreign Body Removal (n = 173)

Figure 11: Tympanic Membrane Status after Foreign Body Removal (n = 173)

Study Flow Diagram

Figure 12: Study Flow Diagram

Figure 12: Study Flow Diagram – Enrollment and Analysis of Pediatric Patients with Ear Foreign Bodies

Discussion

Foreign bodies of the ear remain a common presentation in pediatric otorhinolaryngology practice, particularly in developing countries where children frequently have access to small household objects and may present late to tertiary care centers. The present study evaluated the frequency and pattern of ear foreign bodies among

pediatric patients presenting to the ENT Department of Ayub Teaching Hospital and demonstrated that ear foreign bodies are predominantly encountered in younger children, with inorganic objects being the most common type.

In the current study, the majority of patients belonged to the 4–6 years age group (39.3%), followed by children aged 7–10 years. This finding is consistent with the exploratory behavior typically observed in preschool and early school-age children. Similar age predominance has been reported in several published studies. Prasad and Harley (2020), in their review of pediatric aural foreign bodies, reported that most cases occurred in children younger than 8 years of age¹⁰. Likewise, Aksakal (2020), in a review of 829 ENT foreign body cases, found that younger children constituted the majority of presentations¹¹. The higher frequency in this age group may be explained by increased curiosity, tendency to imitate peers, and lack of awareness regarding potential harm.

Male predominance was observed in the present study, with males accounting for 59% of cases. This finding is in agreement with several regional and international studies. Ogah (2018) reported male predominance in patients presenting with aural foreign bodies¹². Similarly, Mukherjee et al. (2011) also documented a slightly higher frequency among male children¹³. Although the exact reason remains uncertain, greater outdoor activity, increased physical play, and comparatively more risk-taking behavior among boys may contribute to this pattern.

The present study showed that inorganic foreign bodies were more common than organic foreign bodies, accounting for 57.2% of cases. Beads were the most frequently encountered object, followed by seeds/grains and cotton pieces. These findings are comparable with those reported by Aksakal (2020), who found beads to be the commonest foreign bodies in the ear among children¹¹. Morris et al. (2018) also reported that beads and small toy-related objects were among the most frequent aural foreign bodies requiring hospital management.¹⁴ The frequent occurrence of beads in our study may reflect easy availability of decorative and toy-related items in households. Organic materials such as seeds and grains were also common in our population, which may be related to the rural background of a significant proportion of the study participants.

Right-sided involvement was observed more frequently than left-sided involvement in the present study. Similar findings have been described by Prasad and Harley (2020), who reported right ear predominance in pediatric patients.¹⁰ This pattern is likely related to right-hand dominance in most children, making insertion into the right ear easier and more common. Bilateral foreign bodies were uncommon, which is also consistent with the existing literature.

Regarding clinical presentation, ear pain and irritation were the most common presenting complaints, followed by a history of foreign body insertion and ear discharge. These findings correlate with the observations of Ansley and Cunningham (1998), who reported otalgia, irritation, and hearing-related symptoms as common presentations among children with aural foreign bodies¹⁵. A proportion of children in the present study presented with foul-smelling discharge and bleeding, particularly in cases with delayed presentation or prior attempts at removal. Such presentations highlight the importance of early referral to ENT specialists to minimize complications associated with repeated instrumentation.

Most foreign bodies in the current study were removed without major complications. External auditory canal abrasion was the most common complication observed, while tympanic membrane injury was seen in only a small number of patients. These findings are comparable to those reported by Ogah (2018), who observed minor canal injuries and occasional tympanic membrane trauma in patients undergoing foreign body removal¹². Similarly, DiMuzio and Deschler (2002) reported that complications are usually minor when removal is performed carefully by trained personnel¹⁶. The low complication rate in our study may be attributed to early ENT evaluation and removal under appropriate visualization and instrumentation.

The study also demonstrated that a majority of patients belonged to rural areas. This finding may reflect the referral pattern to Ayub Teaching Hospital, which serves a large rural population of HAZARA, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and adjacent

regions. Lower parental awareness, delayed healthcare-seeking behavior, and limited access to specialized ENT services in peripheral areas may contribute to the burden of pediatric ear foreign bodies in such populations. Similar concerns regarding delayed presentation and inappropriate initial handling have been highlighted in studies from developing countries^{17,18}

The findings of the present study have practical implications for routine ENT practice. Identification of the commonly encountered foreign bodies and their presenting features may help clinicians in prompt diagnosis and management. Public awareness regarding supervision of young children and avoidance of small detachable objects may reduce the incidence of such cases. Furthermore, primary healthcare providers should avoid repeated blind attempts at removal and refer difficult cases early to specialized ENT centers.

Strengths of the Study

This study provides recent local data regarding the frequency and pattern of ear foreign bodies among pediatric patients presenting to a tertiary care ENT department in northern Pakistan. The study was conducted at Ayub Teaching Hospital, which is a major referral center serving both urban and rural populations, thereby allowing inclusion of patients from diverse socioeconomic and geographic backgrounds.

An adequate sample size was included over the study period, which improved the reliability of the observed demographic and clinical patterns. In addition, the study specifically focused on aural foreign bodies in children rather than combining ear, nose, and throat foreign bodies together, allowing a more detailed assessment of pediatric ear foreign bodies as a distinct clinical entity. Standardized clinical evaluation and management by ENT personnel also helped maintain consistency in diagnosis and documentation.

The findings of the study are clinically relevant for routine pediatric ENT practice, particularly in resource-limited tertiary care settings where such cases are frequently encountered.

Limitations of the Study

The present study has certain limitations. As it was a single-center descriptive cross-sectional study, the findings may not be fully generalizable to the overall pediatric population of the country. Patients presenting to a tertiary care hospital may also represent relatively more symptomatic or referred cases, which could introduce referral bias. The cross-sectional design of the study limited the ability to assess long-term outcomes and delayed complications following removal of ear foreign bodies. In addition, follow-up evaluation of patients after discharge was not performed routinely, therefore late sequelae such as persistent canal injury or hearing-related complications could not be assessed.

The study mainly described the frequency and pattern of ear foreign bodies and did not evaluate factors associated with delayed presentation, parental awareness, or healthcare-seeking behavior, which may also influence the clinical presentation and outcomes of these patients.

Conclusion

Ear foreign bodies are a common pediatric ENT presentation at Ayub Teaching Hospital, particularly among younger children and male patients. Inorganic foreign bodies, especially beads, were the most frequently encountered objects, while seeds and grains were the commonest organic foreign bodies. Right-sided ear involvement and symptoms such as ear pain, irritation, and discharge were commonly observed at presentation.

Most cases were managed successfully with minimal complications when evaluated and treated promptly in a specialized ENT setting. Early recognition, appropriate referral, and careful removal under proper visualization remain important to reduce morbidity associated with pediatric ear foreign bodies. Increased parental awareness regarding supervision of children and avoidance of small detachable objects may further help in preventing such presentations.

Additional information

Conflicts of Interest: None

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